

1 **ABC transporter multi-drug resistance genes (“pumps”) in humans with non-small cell lung**
2 **cancer.**

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7 ABC family ATP-binding cassette transporter pumps support resistance to clinical interventions that use
8 classical genotoxic chemotherapies based on the presumed ability of the transporter cassette to export the
9 chemotherapy from the cytosol, preventing access to the microtubule cytoskeleton or the host genomic
10 DNA. We describe here a network of ABC family transporters containing *ABCB6*, *ABCF3*, as well as
11 genes of the ABCC transporter family including *ABCC1*, *ABCC3*, *ABCC5* and *ABCC10*, expressed in the
12 type of cancer that results in highest morbidity in man, non-small cell lung cancer, which together likely
13 support chemoresistance.

14 Citations

15 1. Robey, R.W., Pluchino, K.M., Hall, M.D., Fojo, A.T., Bates, S.E. and Gottesman, M.M., 2018.
16 Revisiting the role of ABC transporters in multidrug-resistant cancer. *Nature Reviews Cancer*, 18(7),
17 pp.452-464.